

Mapping gender in the transforming research life cycle

Vilte Banelytė¹ Vilius Stančiauskas¹ Vitalis Nakrošis¹ and Edit Görögh²

¹ PPMI, Vilnius Lithuania

² University of Göttingen. 37073 Göttingen, Germany

1. Introduction

Opening up the research process is meant to make academic research more inclusive and transparent. In a broader sense, opening up research is part of democratization of research and emancipation of research subjects and citizens generally. However, openness in itself does not guarantee inclusion.

Within OpenUP, a 30-month EC-funded project to primary objectives are to (1) increase knowledge and use of innovative methods for review, dissemination and impact measurement, and (2) advance a more open and gender-sensitive science system. Thus, besides developing a cohesive framework for the review-disseminate-assess phases of the research life cycle that is fit to support and promote Open Science, the findings are translated to a set of concrete recommendations taking into account existing and emerging practices, tools and behavior's, as well as the requirements on quality, openness, gender and age aspects.

Through our desk research and interviews, we identified areas relevant to the themes of the OpenUP project covering gender bias in:

- Publication peer review process;
- Editorial boards;
- Review panels;
- Research dissemination;
- Research and researcher evaluation.

Here we present our findings from desk research and interviews in the areas above. Whereas desk research helped identify specific issues and provide an overview of the current situation, interviews with gender experts provided inputs on various practices and initiatives promoted nationally or by some researcher to improve gender equity in research and academia.

2. Gender bias in the peer review process

One of the factors that contributes to gender inequality in academia is the gender bias associated with the peer review process. Since humans are susceptible to cognitive biases, unrelated to the merit of science, they affect the judgment of reviewers in peer reviews. Throughout the interviews, many respondents revealed that explicit and implicit biases threaten the objectivity of peer reviews, because knowing the gender of an author or reviewer of the paper impacts behaviour and how people conduct themselves. Many interviewees stated that this is favourable to men as more of them are invited to conduct peer reviews than women. Multiple studies confirmed that the attributes of

referees, such as gender and region, can act as determinants of a referee's handling of manuscripts, particularly in terms of the number of manuscripts being reviewed, review time and rejection rate (Grod 2018).

Some argued that OPR could, in fact, escalate gender imparity in peer review. Researchers, particularly female, who are already in more vulnerable positions due to biases against their gender, might be considerably affected by the open identity aspect of the process.¹

Furthermore, the lack of diversity on editorial boards generates disparities in editorial and peer reviews, which also contributes to gender disparities in scholarly communication. Many interviewees argued that governing boards have to be more diverse to be able to collectively overcome issues related to biases. Additionally, the lack of data proving such disparities and their effects does not allow to make data driven decisions.

3. Gender bias in research dissemination

Gender imbalance across many fields science knowledge production (what questions are asked, how analysis is conducted), application (what discoveries are selected for innovation, who is involved in idea creation) and communication (who is perceived as the target audience) across all the mediums. Therefore, it is necessary to apply gender analysis to every step of the research process from designing a search strategy for the literature to identify background, to collection and analysis of data, to drawing conclusions and identifying shortcomings, and communicating results.

OpenUP identified four relevant gender aspects that we have analysed in context of our innovative dissemination case studies (Kraker 2017). The first aspect relates to the gender distribution within the team responsible for research and dissemination. The second aspect pertains to the representation of gender, gender sensitivity and inclusiveness of the disseminated materials. The third aspect regards gender sensitivity and inclusiveness of the used dissemination tools, platforms and strategies. Finally, the fourth gender aspect relates to the target audience, e.g. their gender distribution, and any relevant gender-sensitive aspects in their regard (e.g. when disseminating research results from medicine). Members of the scientific societies and journal editors among the interviewees supported identification of such aspects when disseminating research. Other respondents, particularly researchers, however, insisted that gender-regulating measures in dissemination would not be able to achieve gender equity, but on the contrary, add additional requirements and workload to researchers, preventing them from conducting research.

4. Gender bias in research evaluation

Innovative dissemination tools also have the potential to help women to gain better recognition of their expertise and assist them in putting that expertise forward into the community. The OpenUP survey found that female researchers are more likely to disseminate their research through non-traditional dissemination methods and to engage

¹ https://www.nature.com/articles/nn0399_197

the public (press releases, popular science publications and events for general public) compared to male researchers (Kraker 2017). These efforts, however, are not acknowledged by traditional evaluation methods and research impact measurements. Many respondents especially stakeholders from research/academia and publishers insisted that it is therefore essential not only to equip each female researcher with adequate information and tools to promote their research and expertise but also to introduce ways to recognise and measure their efforts to use innovative tools. These actions may improve the recognition of female researchers, as it would take dissemination through non-traditional dissemination channels into account.

Altmetrics could potentially improve the recognition and evaluation of female researchers because it offers the possibility to implement a more comprehensive evaluation of individuals. Throughout the interviews, it was often noted that women are vastly underrepresented among the most productive researchers. In some cases, this may be due to the fact that women tend to engage in more interdisciplinary research.

Interviewed service providers and researchers argued that if article-level metrics were combined with author level metrics instead of using the Impact Factor, a more diverse set of measures and greater levels of transparency would allow to more accurately depict each researcher's levels of productivity. While, article-level metrics refer to a measure of impact that draws from a variety of different data sources, including traditional (e.g. times cited) and new (e.g. tweets),² author level metrics are defined as an attempt to quantify impact by analysing citations of an individual author's publications.³ Thus, interviewees called for a more extensive use of the combination of these metrics as they have different but complementary abilities to capture impact of each individual researcher much more accurately, including females.

5. Conclusions and further steps: Open Science and RRI to advance gender equality in research

Despite some progress in the past decade, gender inequity in research and academia is still evident. National initiatives at country levels aim to raise awareness on the issue and promote practices that could increase gender equity. In addition, various initiatives are introduced by research organisations, funders and publishers that aim to decrease the gender bias in *reviews-assess-disseminate* cycle of scholarly publishing. Aspects of OS or RRI also offer some solutions by introducing transparency and inclusiveness to this cycle. However, they also pose risks and many researchers and other stakeholders still question their unconditional applicability and implementation.

The OpenUP project continues research in this area. Our research team is dedicated to identify key issues as well as good practices related to gender in peer review, dissemination and altmetrics. The final objective of the project is to produce policy recommendations for peer review, impact measurement and research dissemination highlighting gender-specific good practices.

² <https://sparcopen.org/our-work/article-level-metrics/>

³ <http://libguides.einstein.yu.edu/c.php?g=123507&p=808389>

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